

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D6.8 Policy Briefings v3

WP6 - Dissemination and
Communication

Version: 1

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
CNR	National Research Council Italy
CRUI	Conference of Rectors of Italian Universities
CSO	Civil Society Organisation
ECE NTUA	National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computing Engineering
EDC	Equality and Diversity Committee
EPB	Ecole Polytechnique de Bruxelles
FUNCOM	Collaboration with Fundraising and Communication Department
GE	Gender Equality
GEC	Gender Equality Committee
GMUS	Grant Management Unified Electronic System
HE	Higher Education
HR	Human Resources
iGEP	Inclusive Gender Equality Plan
IRB	Institute for Research in Biomedicine
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
R&I	Research & Innovation
SRNSFG	Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics
STU BA	Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava
UEFISCDI	Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania
ULB	Université Libre de Bruxelles
UNILE	Salento university

UZG FER	University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing
(GEP) WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
YU	Yasar University

Executive Summary

Deliverable *D6.8 – Policy Briefings v3* is the third (final) series of policy briefings linked with Task 6.4 – Development of Policy briefings and final conference. The deliverable includes one European and nine national policy briefings developed collaboratively by VIL and the CALIPER's RPOs/RFOs respectively.

The briefings featured in this deliverable are mainly addressed to the management of Higher Education Institutions, RPOs and RFOs, officers in governmental bodies, and agencies in charge of Gender Equality, Higher Education, and Research & Innovation at European, regional and national level. In addition, the briefings are targeted to policymakers, while they can also serve as guide and practical tool for other Horizon Europe consortia aiming at achieving structural changes towards gender equality.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

Within CALIPER's project lifecycle, two series of policy briefings have been prepared in corresponding deliverables, while the present deliverable presents the third (final) series of policy briefings. Each deliverable consists of a policy brief targeted at European level and nine policy briefs at national level. In both cases the input stems from the collaboration of VIL, as T6.4 leader, and the GEP implementing RPOs and RFOs of the project. The aim of these policy briefs is to link Research & Innovation with Gender Equality. To do so, the policy briefs reflect the ongoing findings and the experience gained during the CALIPER's efforts in relation to the development and implementation of inclusive GEPs.

The current deliverable, *D6.8 Policy briefing v3*, is the third, and final, version of the above-described series of outputs. Each of the three policy briefing versions follows a specific thematic area according to the progress of the project and the stages for a GEP development and implementation. The list below describes the focus areas of each of the policy briefing "versions":

- 1st version: Policy briefing v1: Focusing on the design and development of a GEP
- 2nd version: Policy briefing v2: Focusing on the implementation of a GEP
- 3rd version: Policy briefing v3: Focusing on the monitoring and of a GEP

The current deliverable is aimed at European and national (Croatian, Georgian, Slovakian, Belgian, Greek, Spanish, Romanian, Turkish and Italian) stakeholders who are implementing equality measures in their institutions, such as change agents in HE institutions, public/private organisation, RPO/RFOs, HR professionals, top and middle management and researchers including also potentially policymakers at European and national level.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 introduces the purpose and scope of the deliverable along with its linkages with other WPs and Tasks.
- Chapter 2 describes the approach followed for the preparation of the policy briefs, their aim, structure and their target audiences.
- Chapter 3 presents the policy briefings developed at the European and national levels by VIL and each corresponding RPO/RFO. A total of 10 briefings are included in this deliverable.
- Chapter 4 includes a few final remarks on the deliverable.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

This deliverable is part of Task 6.4 – Development of Policy briefings and final conference of WP6 Dissemination and Communication, aiming at producing key policy briefings to reflect the findings and experiences gained during the project's lifetime. This task is focused on distilling key policy related learning points from WP4 on Monitoring and Evaluation of Gender Equality Plans. It contributes to T5.3 – Raising awareness and engagement activities and T5.4 – Sustaining and replicating in STEM as these tasks aimed at creating a favourable environment for accepting and sustaining the GEPs. Furthermore, it contributes to T6.3 – External communication and multiplying effect.

Last but not least, this deliverable is interlinked with, WP3 implementation of GEPs, and WP4 Monitoring and Evaluation given that it draws its content from these WPs.

2 Policy briefings' approach

2.1 Policy briefings' aim

The third version of the CALIPER policy briefings serves as practical evidence of the GEP implementation process at each GEP implementing partner, transferring the knowledge that the CALIPER consortium has gained so far via the structural change process that has been introduced after the implementation of the first and second iteration phase of the gender equality measures foreseen in their approved GEP.

It presents to the target audience recommendations that stem from CALIPER experience and revolve around facilitating the evaluation process of a GEP. The recommendations at the European level refer to broader concepts that have been elaborated within the project's implementation, while the recommendations at the National level result from GEP implementing RPOs/RFOs involved in the project and draw from their relevant national/regional, legal framework, unique experiences and conclusions coming from their own monitoring and evaluation efforts.

Upon the approval of each version of the briefings from the European Commission, the content of the briefings is transferred into shorter and easy to read templates for their dissemination. These templates feature schemes and note boxes to present the information in a more appealing way. These final versions are uploaded on the CALIPER [website](#), and disseminated through the CALIPER online channels, as well as through project partners' ones. What is more, the policy briefs can be potentially translated into each RPO/RFOs national language, to increase the engagement of the national target audience.

2.2 Policy briefings' target audience

The policy briefing is an action-oriented tool targeting practitioners interested and/or active in a specific policy domain, in this case, related to Gender Equality in R&I.

The primary target audience of the CALIPER policy briefs consists of management of Higher Education Institutions, RPOs and RFOs, officers in governmental bodies, and agencies in charge of Gender Equality, Higher Education, and Research & Innovation at European, regional and national level. In addition, the briefings are targeted to policymakers, while they can also serve as guide and practical tool for other Horizon Europe consortia aiming at achieving structural changes towards gender equality.

2.3 CALIPER policy briefings' structure

Both the European and national policy briefings were created based on the CALIPER experience of the first and second iteration phases of the GEPs implementation.

The European policy brief includes four parts:

1. An introduction that lays out the focus of the current version and explains the importance of sharing insights regarding the monitoring and evaluation of GEPs as those derived from the CALIPER project experience as a whole.
2. The second part outlines the methodology used for monitoring and evaluating the implemented GEPs in the RPOs/RFOs of the CALIPER project. The methodology was based on two main pillars/methods. Both formative and summative evaluation methods were in place from the beginning of the project for assessing the progress and impact of the gender equality interventions.

3. The third and main part where the recommendations are presented, and a brief description is provided for each of them.
4. A concluding part to summarise and point out the goal sought through the assessment of GEPs by CALIPER partners.

In terms of the national briefs, all of them share the same structure in order to ensure consistency. A common introductory part is provided to establish the context under which the input from each partner RPO/RFO unfolds.

Then, each national brief unfolds in three parts:

1. In first part, each RPO/RFO explains the national context regarding the GEP assessment procedures.
2. The second part entails the relevant recommendations, proposed based on RPOs/RFOs unique experience following the project's action monitoring and evaluation plan/methodology.
3. The third part provides a conclusion underlining the key takeaways.

3 CALIPER's policy briefings

This chapter contains the 10 policy briefings that the CALIPER project has developed within the third version of policy briefings. First, the European briefing is presented, followed by the nine national briefings from the seven RPOs and two RFOs participating in the project.

3.1 European Policy Briefing

Introduction

CALIPER aims to bring about institutional change in research performing and funding organisations by designing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating inclusive Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) contributing to a more gender equal, inclusive, and democratic Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystems.

The CALIPER series of policy briefs (three in total) focus on sharing policy recommendations based on key thematic areas 1. design and development, 2. implementation, 3. monitoring and evaluation of inclusive GEPs (the focus of the present third and final policy brief).

GEPs have been made an eligibility criterion for accessing Horizon Europe funding as they have been considered a tool for achieving change towards Gender equality in R&I (Ljubljana Declaration, 2021) exerting noticeable impact on the national gender equality activities in R&I, which is demonstrated particularly by the increase in approved GEPs in R&I institutions ([Knapińska & Chrobak-Tatara, 2023](#)). This policy change foresees that GEPs have specific mandatory process-related requirements and cover recommended areas of intervention: data collection and monitoring are one of those mandatory features for GEPs as it is established that data should feed in the GEP's objectives and, indicators, as well as its ongoing evaluation of progress¹.

However, monitoring and evaluation systems for GEPs are a key challenge for research organisations but have the potential to draw insights across Europe as regards transformative potential of GEPs in terms of changing institutional culture ([Knapińska & Chrobak-Tatara, 2023](#)).

This challenge is aimed to be tackled within the present brief. The research work done during the CALIPER project led to a number of insights about the requirements for a sound and meaningful monitoring and evaluation of inclusive gender equality interventions within R&I ecosystems. Apart from these, the present brief reflects on how EU policy makers can advance ERA on this topic. After describing the methodology followed for monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs our recommendations on this process are presented, which are aimed at the staff and management of higher education Institutions, staff and management of governmental bodies, and agencies in charge of gender equality, higher education and research institutions as well as policy makers in R&I at European, regional, and national level.

Background: CALIPER methodology on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs

Most work on GEPs in the ERA to date has focused on capacity building and GEP development. Now, in reference to this work, it is important that we bring attention to how we can establish robust monitoring and evaluation systems for assessing to what extent inclusive GEPs can act as drivers of institutional change towards gender equality.

¹wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf (europa.eu)

The CALIPER project has provided a valuable methodology for monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs, offering a structured approach to assess the partners inclusive gender equality interventions throughout their GEPs implementation (For more information see [D4.1 – Formative Evaluation methodology](#)).

The CALIPER methodology was based on two main pillars/methods. Both formative and summative evaluation methods were in place from the beginning of the project for assessing the progress and impact of the gender equality interventions. In particular:

- **The formative evaluation** took the form of a self-evaluation process running throughout the project's duration focusing on gathering data while an action is being implemented, to ensure its alignment with the planned progress of the partner's inclusive GEP.
- **The summative evaluation** involved external, independent experts at the beginning and near the conclusion of the project for assessing the extent to which the anticipated outcomes from the specific inclusive gender equality interventions included in the partners' GEP were achieved.

Overall, the formative evaluation assesses the design and implementation of the GEPs, functioning as a toolkit for crafting well-designed interventions. The summative evaluation, on the other hand, is focused on outputs, outcomes, and impact that those interventions have brought to the institution. The formative evaluation complements the summative evaluation, as it helps clarify the reasons behind certain outcomes and impacts achieved in relation also to the design and implementation of GEP activities.

Both methods utilize qualitative and quantitative data: the former are collected via interviews and focus groups, providing an avenue to explore participants' experiences and facilitate the exchange of ideas, while the latter follow up on specific indicators for each inclusive gender equality intervention.

CALIPER recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs

Mixed methodology: gather quantitative and qualitative data both for a short and long term period

Measuring GEP outcomes and impacts can be a complex exercise. Structural change is a dynamic process that mobilizes knowledge and skills, and at the same time creates challenges in each step, often resulting in a substantial time gap between the initiation of GEP activities and the emergence of outcomes. Consequently, it is necessary to use a mixed methodology by collecting both quantitative and qualitative data through a set of tools spanning from questionnaires, semi structured interviews, focus groups, observations, feedback forms and data analysis with a wide range of stakeholders and project participants. The quantitative and qualitative data analysis can be complemented by data visualization tools such as Networks Maps, Outputs Impacts and Stakeholders Matrix.

In addition, data should be collected over a short- and long-term period to enable the drawing of robust conclusions about the effectiveness of the specific intervention.

Monitoring data offers valuable insights into the quality of the implementation process. Organisations can use the formative evaluation methodology employed in the CALIPER project which based on the Horizon 2020 [EFFORTI](#) project highlighting also the importance of building on the knowledge generated across previously EU funded projects on the topic, to supervise and guide the implementation of their GEP interventions.

It is essential to incorporate evaluation right from the initial steps during the GEP design to make sure that effective feedback loops are in place, which will strengthen the implementation process.

Collaboration: involvement of internal and external stakeholders

External impartial evaluators: having an external evaluator involved in the process of monitoring and evaluating GEPs can ensure a more objective review of the results, but also make sure that the relevant gender equality knowledge is in place to assess the institutions status quo with regards to gender equality.

Internal stakeholders: appoint one staff member or a Task Force/Working Group as internal reference to safeguard the evaluation process. This person or team should coordinate internal data collection and liaise with external evaluator(s) for creating ownership and engagement at the institutional level and engagement.

In addition, involving in the evaluation process institutional members who have played a role in conceptualizing the intervention, enables the incorporation of diverse perspectives and experiences into the change process making it more inclusive.

Adopt a feminist perspective: ground the evaluation process in feminist interpretations of experiential, reflexive and organizational learning theories.

Through evaluative actions grounded in feminist interpretations of experiential, reflexive and organisational learning theories, a collaborative reflection over strengths and weak points will be activated and will eventually lead to reshaping and adjusting actions along the way.

Shifting away from simple, linear cause-effect models when assessing the impact of interventions, considering the institution's specific context will lead to an increased emphasis on impacts.

Organise dedicated awareness sessions for monitoring and evaluation

Organise periodic evaluation webinars and face to face sessions for supporting and guiding the involved stakeholders through the methodological monitoring and evaluations process as well as their respective results.

CALIPER recommendations for advancing ERA for gender equality via inclusive GEPs

Framing inclusive gender equality policies with context-sensitive approaches

Different National and local gender equality policies and cultures influence and impact on gender equality interventions and programs in various ways. Stakeholders and policy makers active within the European Research Area, can capitalise on the extensive knowledge already produced on these topics that shows uneven levels of advancement and effectiveness of gender mainstreaming in HEIs as well as in Research and Innovation, especially in Widening countries. This applies also to the way inclusiveness and intersectionality are received and integrated in those policies, or rather resisted in some cases.

Building capacity and exchanging knowledge

There is an ongoing need for the (gender) change agents and practitioners to receive training on how to set up, implement and monitor inclusive GEPs (e.g. on how to gather and analyse intersectional gender disaggregated data). Ad hoc capacity building and training as well as knowledge exchange events among institutions on these topics are still highly needed across Europe and should be prioritized within ERA policies in the upcoming years.

Monitoring progress

It is essential to follow up on the implementation and impact of GEPs because since their introduction as an eligibility criterion within Horizon Europe framework programme, there was a considerable increase in approved GEPs in R&I institutions and quantity might risk prevailing over quality of inclusive GEPs. EU policy

makers need to continue in the existing efforts of closely monitoring the implementation of GEPs across EU countries and provide evidence on their uptake and impact.

Gendering research

There is an ongoing need for transforming Research and Innovation ecosystems to become more inclusive. Evidence still suggests that there is a considerable lack of integration of the gender lenses in Research and Innovation processes. Considering the existing expertise and knowledge on these topics, there is a need for continuing to provide guidelines to RPOs and RFOs, including specific cases from different disciplines as well as capacity building programs and mutual learning opportunities.

Conclusion

CALIPER's series of Policy briefs is the project's contribution to shape future policy developments at national and European level, putting the spotlight on the project's experience to reinforce and support changes for a more gender equal and democratic research and innovation ecosystems.

The evaluation of GEPs is an indispensable practice for organisations striving to create more inclusive and equitable workplaces. Even though there are challenges in measuring the outcomes and impact of GEPs, organisations can embrace the insights and methods outlined by CALIPER to embark on a meaningful journey towards change, contributing to a future where inclusive gender equality is not just a plan but a standard practice.

3.2 National Policy Briefings

Introduction

The present policy brief provides insights into the presence/absence of a national/regional monitoring system for inclusive GEPs as well as recommendations supporting the development/operation of such systems drawing from the CALIPER project for supporting institutional change for promoting inclusive gender equality in the new ERA.

This is particularly relevant, since the most recent framework programme (9th in line, 2021-2027), known as Horizon Europe, made gender mainstreaming in research more binding for Member States. Among other things, it focused on GEPs in universities and research organisations as key tools to combat gender inequalities and other discrimination. In order to receive funding for research and technology projects, it is an eligibility criterion that all public institutions (universities, research centres, research and innovation organisations, etc.) have a GEP. This foresees that GEPs have specific mandatory process-related requirements and cover recommended areas of intervention: data collection and monitoring are one of those mandatory features for GEPs as it is established that data should inform the GEP's objectives and targets, indicators, and ongoing evaluation of progress.

3.2.1 University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (UZG-FER)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

In Croatia, there are policies in place to promote gender equality such as:

- Article 14 of the Act on Gender Equality states that public institutions are required to work towards gender balance but have the freedom to define and monitor their gender equality policies.

- Article 3 of the Act on Gender Equality states that educational institutions and research performing organizations are obliged to conduct educational programs about gender equality for staff members and that they have to promote gender equality and elimination of inequalities, stereotypes and prejudices in the education process at all levels.
- Public administration bodies which are mainly owned by the state, should introduce quotas and employ legal persons to facilitate the adaptation of the GEP.

The Gender Equality Act (and other regulations) are monitored by the National Office for Gender Equality, which was established in 2004 by the Croatian Government.

However, GEPs are not a mandatory requirement for research performing organizations and there are no mechanisms in place supporting the GEP design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation process. In addition, there is no national or regional system that audits the GEP's implementation.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Allocate national resources to trainings for RPOs on the topic for the GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation

RPOs that usually have a low number of female students and researchers are in the area of STEM and do not have internal capacity to tackle topics in gender equality. Therefore, external experts for both, gender equality and implementation of GEP, are needed. It would be helpful if the Ministry of Education and Science or other government agencies could provide these training sessions.

Allocate national resources for meetings with other national/international institutions to discuss issues and find solutions on the GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation

Currently there is no national platform for meeting and discussing this topic. The opportunity to meet and discuss joint issues is crucial for the topics which are in common to all RPOs.

Create a national public database of GEP and/or good GE practices

During the development of GEP, often discussion arises if the proposed action is following national regulations. Existence of a national database of good practices would be often beneficial in resolving these issues.

Establish national/regional support systems to GEPs evaluation in general

Every institutional action benefits from monitoring and evaluation that examines if its relevant goals/objectives are being met. It would be beneficial to be able to receive external evaluation of the implementation of the GEP. National audit could enable creation of national criteria for GEPs which currently do not exist. It is important that national audits are in compliance with eligibility conditions to receive funding from the framework Horizon Europe.

Conclusion

UZG-FER was one of the first RPOs in Croatia to implement a GEP. The support received through the CALIPER project, both through funding and knowledge transfer, was essential in the pioneering work of the customized creation and implementation of a GEP. Key factors for obtaining strong institutional support for gender equality were:

- encouraging personal engagement of employees in the process from the beginning;
- a working group consisting of influential employees to develop the GEP; and
- evidence based arguments to support the GEP, support from the high management and EU perspective.

However, there are limits to what a research institution can do by itself; structural issues in the research and innovation system must be tackled on the national level and with the support of the national and regional lawmakers and funding providers. National funding and a platform for development, implementation and evaluation of GEPs is necessary to make further progress in inclusive gender equality.

3.2.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

Having a GEP in place institutions has increased value within the Georgian Science communities since applying for funding from European programmes like Horizon 2020/Horizon EU has been becoming mandatory. However, GEPs are not mandatory for research organizations according to national laws and policies. Besides that, there is no mechanism in place creating a favourable environment for the development, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of GEPs at national level.

Since there is no mandatory requirement for GEPs on national level, there is no national/regional support for GEPs design and implementation or monitoring and evaluation consequently. What is more, there is no audit system for the implemented GEPs.

However, it is worth mentioning that over the last years, supporting Gender Equality has been becoming an important dimension tackled by the Georgian Government and very substantial steps have been successfully taken in this regard.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Establish a national mechanism or appoint contact points and external evaluators to the GEP activities

Setting a national mechanism and assigning contact points would formalise the national policy's approach to the implementation of Gender Equality Plans for research organisations across the country. A national mechanism can offer a central point of reference for all the organisations that seek to design and put in place GE strategies. External evaluators under the jurisdiction of such mechanism and its contact points can afford that credible and uniformed evaluation procedures are utilized within the GEP implementing research organisations.

Establish national/regional support systems to GEPs monitoring and evaluation in general

A standardised set of monitoring and evaluation resources provided by official support systems can be aligned with the overall formal and uniformed national mechanism and ensure that GEP implementation is assessed based on adequate criteria.

Allocate additional resources for different purposes such as organization of meetings, workshops, training

Capacity building should be a key priority in national and regional level. Organisations that seek to design, implement and evaluate a Gender Equality Plans need assistance/guidance throughout all these steps.

Create a national public database of GEP and/or good GE practices

A resource vault accessible via a national mechanism can offer credible and validated tools, methods and approaches to research organisations and help them base their GEPs on existing practises that proved to be of certain efficiency.

Conclusion

The Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (SRNSFG) implemented its first GEP throughout the CALIPER project lifecycle. Delivering a GEP and assessing its implementation in the context of the project, enabled SRNSFG to experience an action plan that has been innovative at national level.

Hence to the above, it has been made quite evident that the establishment of a central mechanism that will be responsible of providing adequate resources and validated tools and methods for the development, implementation and evaluation of GEPs is of essential importance to make a step forward regarding the integration of gender balance and the gender dimension in research organisations across the country.

The afore-listed recommendations can help to create a regulatory system for GEP implementation and its systematic monitoring and evaluation on national level. In addition to the above, it will be beneficial to share the experiences among different institutions related to GEPs' elaboration and implementation.

3.2.3 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (STU BA)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

The Slovak legislation has not amended the gender equality plan. Gender equality is primarily regulated by the Anti-Discrimination Act No. 365/2004 Coll. on equal treatment in some areas and on protection against discrimination and on amendments to some laws and the Labor Code. Compliance with the principle of equal treatment consists in the prohibition of discrimination on the grounds of sex, religion or belief, race, belonging to a nationality or ethnic group, disability, age, sexual orientation, marital and family status, skin colour, language, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, gender or other status or because of reporting criminality or other anti-social activity.

When observing the principle of equal treatment, it is also necessary to consider good morals for the purpose of extending protection against discrimination. Compliance with the principle of equal treatment also consists in taking measures to protect against discrimination. The requirement to create a GEP comes from EU conditions in relation to the provision of grants when submitting project proposals. The goal is to support women in science through the guarantees of organizations performing research.

It should be, also, noted that issues of gender equality belong to the management of the Ministry of Labour, Social Affairs and Family of the Slovak Republic. The Department of Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities is the gender equality body in Slovakia assigned with the coordination of the state policy on gender equality and empowerment of women. The department serves as the body responsible for the coordination of the implementation of horizontal and equal opportunities in the projects co-financed by European framework funds. The Department of Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities is responsible for the coordination of the Committee on Gender Equality which is a standing committee of the Government Council for Human Rights, Minorities and Gender Equality.

In November 2010, the Council of Government of the Slovak Republic for Human Rights, National Minorities and Gender Equality was set up as a permanent advisory body of the Government of the Slovak Republic. Based on this, many important systemic changes were introduced also in the fields related to anti-discrimination, promising positive impacts in the field of communication of the government with NGOs, as well as in coordination of human rights in general and anti-discrimination in particular. According to its statute, the council became a permanent expert, advisory, coordinating and consultative body of the government in the field of human rights including the rights of national minorities and ethnic groups and in the field of pursuing the principle of equal treatment and the principle of gender equality.

The Committee is a permanent expert body of the Council of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Human Rights, National Minorities and Gender Equality on issues related to gender equality and for the Implementation of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (CEDAW). The committee acts as a consultative body on matters of gender equality under the Constitution of the Slovak Republic

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Create a set of indicators tailored to the national level for monitoring GE

The indicators should be set by statistical analysis pointing to a positive trend in their development. The indicators should be based on what the purpose of the gender equality plan is. GEPs are unique to each organization, however, it is possible to set this statistical reporting in general, such as tracking the number of women in management positions (however, it must be stated what the management positions are), the amount of variable remuneration in the same positions for men and women. For

example, in Slovakia, the Statistical Office annually publishes statistics on the remuneration of men and women.

Establish a national mechanism or appoint contact points and external evaluators to the GEP activities

As mentioned above, there is an effectiveness in establishing an advisory body for gender equality plans directly under the management of The Department of Gender Equality and Equal Opportunities, which would appoint expert members and advisors.

Allocate additional resources for different purposes such as organization of meetings, workshops, training

Capacity building should be a key priority in national and regional level. Organisations that seek to design, implement and evaluate a Gender Equality Plan need assistance/guidance throughout all these steps.

Create a national public database of GEP and/or good GE practices

A resource vault accessible via a national mechanism can offer credible and validated tools, methods and approaches to research organisations and help them base their GEPs on existing practises that proved to be of certain efficiency.

Conclusion

Through its involvement with the CALIPER project, STU BA became one of the pioneering Higher Education Institutions that implemented a GEP taking into account the principles set in European Level. Following the project's workplan, STU BA has assessed the conditions of gender equality introduction and gender dimension integration into research, in order to draft a tailored and context-specific GEP.

This experience resulted in a better understanding of the relevant national legal framework. In this respect, it has been made evident that due to the fact that the issue of creation, implementation and evaluation of GEP is not regulated by law, there is no relevant and standardised legal mandate. The afore-mentioned councils and committees of the Slovak Republic can have an advisory function to regulate this area, including the directing of financial support flow support based on a well-rounded reporting of indicators provided by GEP implementing research organisations.

Furthermore, it is suggested that appointing national contact points, gender experts/evaluators and maintaining a central database of good practices could assist on raising awareness and capacity building within GEP implementing research organisations.

3.2.4 Université libre de Bruxelles (ULB)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

At the level of the Fédération Wallonie-Bruxelles (FWB), which is the level of power in charge of research and teaching, the ARES – Académie de Recherche et Enseignement Supérieur – comprises two committees dedicated to gender equality:

The Women and Science Committee (Comité Femmes et Sciences) was created in 2016. It aims to "promote the balanced participation of men and women among university researchers and teaching staff, and to develop a gender policy" through the formulation of opinions and recommendations, and the exchange of information and good practice. It also facilitates implementation of the European Commission's recommendations on the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers and helps define the FWB's position within the Helsinki Group. The "Comité Femmes et Sciences" coordinates with the group of "gender contact persons" at the six FWB universities and the FRS-FNRS (Federal funding agency for research). Created in 2013, this group has 3 missions, that of information, notably through the drafting of an institutional report on the state of gender equality in the universities, that of awareness-raising and that of networking within the universities and the FRS-FNRS. Funded by the FWB within the framework of the Researcher's Charter (EURAXESS), the group of "gender contact persons" ensures an exchange and information role between the Women and Science Committee, the universities and the FRS-FNRS regarding the state of progress of gender policies implemented within institutions.

More recently, in 2020, a second committee was created in the ARES. The Commission for Gender in Higher Education (CoGES) is in charge of dealing with gender issues in higher education and supporting higher education establishments in their fight against gender discrimination. Its missions are to:

- formulate opinions and recommendations on gender-related issues in higher education;
- support higher education establishments in raising awareness and appropriating gender issues;
- support higher education establishments in the fight against gender discrimination and sexual and gender-based violence;
- promote gender-balanced representation in decision-making bodies and across all staff categories;
- promote the attractiveness of gendered fields of study;
- promote gender mainstreaming in all curricula, training, content and research in higher education;
- raise awareness of gender bias in selection and promotion processes for all categories of higher education staff;
- promote a harmonious articulation of life times in higher education, and propose concrete avenues to this end;
- encourage the exchange of information and practices between higher education establishments, the Women and Science Committee, the administration, ministers responsible for higher education, scientific research and women's rights, and relevant bodies at European level.

Regarding employment, Actiris, the regional agency for employment, helps work organizations in the Brussels-Capital region to develop and implement diversity plans. The ULB created its diversity plan in this context and acquired the Actiris Diversity Label in March 2023.

The higher education institutions receive a yearly budget to support the implementation of gender equality actions. The group of "gender contact persons" (see above) collects data on gender equality in their respective universities and creates a report on gender equality every year. Every two years, a common report is created regarding the 6 universities, following guidelines.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Establish a FWB mechanism or appoint contact points and external evaluators to the GEP activities

A body and/or mechanism can be established under the jurisdiction of the above-presented committees and focus on the coordination and monitoring of research organisations that put GEPs into action in their structures and management.

Allocate national resources for meetings with other national/international institutions to discuss issues and find solutions on the GEP implementation, monitoring and evaluation

Capacity building activities can serve as a means by which exchange of knowledge and best practises can be channelled to research organisations and common challenges as well as solutions can stem in a participatory and collaborative fashion.

Allocate additional resources for different purposes such as organization of meetings, workshops, training

Implementing a GEP is a dynamic process for an organisation. Having the appropriate and progressively evolving resources at their disposal, it is essential.

Create a national public database of GEP and/or good GE practices

In addition to the capacity building activities, a focal point, in the form of an official platform, can meet the needs of GEP implementing research organisations for up-to-date and stress-tested tools and procedures for their GEP measures evaluation and enhancement.

Fund universities' access to the national database – Banque carrefour de la sécurité sociale.

This kind of access to aggregated data about the diversity of students and workers on other dimensions of diversity than gender, such as national origins (of the parents), socioeconomic level of the neighbourhood of residence, etc. This would allow for a better monitoring of diversity and intersectionality.

Conclusion

In the context of CALIPER project, ULB has evolved its gender equality strategies and the integration of the dimension of gender in research. Elaborating on the national/regional framework and the creation of targeted interventions in its GEP has been a great learning experience for ULB's institution.

Hence the above efforts, the need for specialised bodies/mechanisms responsible for organising capacity building actions among GEP implementing research organisations and for the delivery of niche data and best practises has been made prominent.

3.2.5 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (NTUA-ECE)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

According to national laws and policies, the design and implementation of GEPs is not mandatory for research organizations. However, *Law 4589/2019* and *Law 4957/2022* foresee the establishment of Gender Equality Committees (GEC) in all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). The same laws also stipulate that the Gender Equality Committees (GECs) are responsible, among others, for the design, implementation and monitor of GEPs. This requirement supports the development and implementation of GEPs.

Additionally, *Law 4957/2022* notes that the GEC may be supported in the implementation of the GEP, by an administrative Unit established by the Institution according to its internal regulations.

As regards the research and technology bodies, *Law 4957/2022* foresees the establishment of GECs and determines that they are responsible among others, for the design, implementation and monitoring of GEPs.

Reports on the design and implementation of GEPs have been published in the framework of research projects. For example, in 2021 the TARGET project published a report on “Gender Equality Action Plans for Higher Education Institutions and Research organizations: Guidelines and tools” prepared by the Hellenic Foundation for European & Foreign Policy. Additionally, the Hellenic Foundation for European & Foreign Policy prepared a report on “Designing together Gender Equality in Higher Education Institutions and Research organizations” in 2023, during its participation in the GENDRHED project.

These publications provide some guidance and support but are not part of an overall national directive or strategy. To the best of our knowledge, there is no national/regional support mechanism on the GEP design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation, nor any support system that audits the GEPs. Such an auditing system would be beneficial, as it would ensure the institution’s engagement, at a high and middle level management.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Communicate relevant official guidelines on the design, implementation and monitoring and evaluation of GEPs at national level

This could be helpful because it shall set a common and concise framework for the design of GEPs.

Provision of grants for the design and implementation of GEPs

Ensuring funding specifically for the GEPs formulation and implementation will further motivate, facilitate and engage institutions to design and implement such strategies/measures.

Law 4604/2019 (article 11) should start being substantially implemented

This Law foresees, among others, the integration of a gender dimension into the state institutions’ budgets (along with a justification for the respective actions), and the implementation of trainings for the staff involved in the budgeting and organizing of activities. The substantial application of the Law will force all state organizations (including Higher Education Institutions - HEIs) to include a gender dimension in their annual state budgets and therefore be able to design and implement effective GEPs.

Include GE indicators in the annual evaluation of HEIs

This would constitute the integration of gender equality through GEPs mandatory and would facilitate the function of a monitoring mechanism.

Establish a central (national level) GEP evaluation framework

This could start with the development of an evaluation methodology and conclude with the creation of an independent evaluation body. This will ensure the continuation of the GEPs, as well as the engagement of the institutions in the design and implementation of actions.

Conclusion

NTUA participated in the CALIPER project to design, develop and implement a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) for the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE). The aim was to establish a well-adapted GEP, to support structural change through improved procedures, policies, and organisational structures. ECE became the first School of the NTUA to successfully put a GEP in practise.

Following the steps of CALIPER methodology, the NTUA-ECE based its GEP into careful examination of the legal context as well as the available guidelines both at European and national level for the formulation of a GEP. The implementation and the evaluation of its strategy have led the NTUA-ECE partners to useful conclusions.

Frist and foremost, there is a need for GEPs design, implementation and evaluation guidelines at central, that is national, level that shall provide a common base for all research organisations that seek to set up a GEP. What is more, there need to be financial incentives in the form of tailored grants for the GEPs implementation, while Law 4604/2019 (article 11) has to be put in place and prompt the allocation of budget for the integration of gender dimension in research.

Finally, a standardised set of gender-related data needs to be aggregated by Higher Education Institutions. Such action will facilitate the introduction of a mandatory mechanism of GEPs evaluation nation-wide.

3.2.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (IRB)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

From March 2022, all the companies/institutions with more than 50 employees are obliged to have a Gender Equality Plan. The legal framework that provides the guidelines and minimum requirements in the preparation and evaluation process of Gender Equality Plans was approved in 2020. (*“Real Decreto 901/2020: Law on regulation and registration of Gender Equality Plans”*) The Royal decree establishes a framework that sets, among other things, minimum requirements, that every GEP document and process should contain. These requirements are the following:

- Assessment/evaluation
- Personal, territorial and temporal scope
- Resources of application
- Monitor and evaluation plan (including qualitative and quantitative data)
- Specific process for modifications and negotiation
- Salary audit results and mechanism (legal framework provided by “ Real Decreto 902/2020”)
- Action Plan (including implementation dates and indicators)
- Internal committee/commission to provide follow-ups and reports

In addition, the *“Real Decreto 901/2020”* provides the minimum requirements for the elaboration of GEPs along with a template including areas of implementation, as well as a template to develop the assessment phase for every company and institute complying to this law. This way the law offers specific guidelines on mandatory requirements that have to be evaluated in the assessment phase of the Gender Equality Plan. The law also indicates that the maximum duration for the development and completion of a GEP is 4 years.

What is more, Spain has done another step forward to creating a better context to the intersectional approach to equality. During the first trimester of 2023, the country approved the *“Ley 4/2023, de 28 de febrero, para la igualdad real y efectiva de las personas trans y para la garantía de los derechos de las personas LGTBI”*. This legislation translates Law, for the real and effective equality of Trans people and guarantees the rights of people LGBTQ+, setting obligatory requirements to be added to GEPs.

Spain has dedicated organisms that support Equality and Diversity, that is the Ministry of Equality (Ministerio de Igualdad). This Ministry is the department of the Spanish Government responsible for the proposal and execution of the government's policy on gender equality, with a focus on making the equality between men and women real and effective as well as on the prevention and eradication of different forms of violence against women. The department's roles also include eradication of all kinds of discrimination by sex, racial and ethnic origin, religion or ideology, sexual orientation, gender identity, age, disability or any other personal or social condition or circumstances.

In addition, it is worth mentioning that the inclusion of equality and diversity topics in the scientific scope has provided a favourable condition to include scientific topics in GEPs. For example, gender perspective in the research content and the gender balance in research groups is now an evaluation criterion for the Spanish Ministry for Science and Technology and for the Catalan Government.

Finally, and also directly linked to the scientific legal scope, in the last quarter of 2022, Spain approved the *“La Ley de la Ciencia, la Tecnología y la Innovación”* (The Law of Science, Technology and Innovation). In regard to gender, the law provides legal security for gender equality in the R&D&I system, ensuring a dual approach, where the gender perspective is a transversal axis of the planning instruments of public agents in science, technology and innovation.

Regarding the evaluation and compliance of GEP implementation and evaluation procedures, companies and institutes may be audited by the Ministry of Labor and Social Economy ensuring compliance with current

legislation and the documents and processes directly related to the elaboration of GEPs such as the assessment phase and salary audit results.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Set orientation and support in the incorporation of gender dimensions into research

In order to comply with the legislative framework, it is valuable to set a concrete roadmap and resources portfolio, that GEP implementing research centers can utilise. Having examples of gender dimension integration into research available should be of great help for research organisations so that they can be able to cover the requirements in a uniformed and concrete approach.

Create a template repository for monitoring and evaluation tools to standardize the GEP evolution for audit purposes

Auditing process constitutes a rigorous task that requires concrete input and resources to be provided by the receiving organisations. To this end, it is essential to compile a cohesive guide that prepares GEP implementing organisations for such processes. A uniformed set of tools and indicators to be applied by the organisations can be of great purpose to standardise auditing processes, thus ensuring transparency, efficient interventions and smooth monitoring and evaluation of GEPs.

Create a dedicated website to communicate the latest legal developments and requirements in regards to the preparation and monitoring of Gender equality and diversity plans

GEP implementing organisations have to navigate themselves among a dynamic legislative framework, that is progressively evolving to cover societal needs and always seeks to enhance the measures for Gender Equality and Diversity. Therefore, a central point of communication of the developments regarding the GEPs design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation can be an important resource at the disposal of organisations so that they can keep updated and always have a credible point of reference for their plans.

Conclusion

IRB has a long-standing record of proactive efforts to establish measures to improve Equality and Diversity at all levels of the organisation. At the same time, the national context regarding gender equality, diversity, inclusiveness and gender dimension into research demonstrates a dynamic legislative framework that prompts organisations to foster GEPs and relevant, supportive measures. Within this context, GEP implementing organisations can be audited by the the Ministry of Labor and Social Economy to validate their strategies compliance with current legislation.

Taking into account the above in conjunction with the Institute's experience through CALIPER's design, implementation and assessment of a unique GEP, IRB puts forward certain recommendations in terms of monitoring and evaluation of GEPs. These recommendations revolve around the orientation of GEP implementing organisations towards the integration of gender in research based on shared concepts, values and examples. What is more, the recommendations note the importance of maintaining central focal points/platforms that can direct GEP implementing organisations according to standardised methods for their plans' monitoring and evaluation, both internally and by external auditors, as well as the role of a platform assigned with the communication of the latest legal developments and requirements for GEPs preparation and evaluation.

3.2.7 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (UEFISCDI)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

In Romania, the commitment to gender equality in research organizations is clearly stated in the Methodological Norms for the Application of Law 202/2002 regarding gender equality and equal opportunities for men and women ([NORME METODOLOGICE din 24 aprilie 2019](#)) which mandates the implementation of action plans addressing the principle of gender equality. This legislation applies to both public and private institutions and emphasizes the promotion of equal opportunities and treatment for women and men, actively seeking to eliminate both direct and indirect gender-based discrimination. It also outlines a detailed system for the evaluation and auditing of implemented GEPs, ensuring that they meet the required standards and objectives.

Furthermore, the National Agency for Equal Opportunities (ANES) plays a pivotal role in shaping the national strategy for gender equality and in monitoring the implementation of GEPs. This regulatory framework, combined with the proactive efforts of institutions like UEFISCDI, which was the first Romanian public institution to develop and implement a GEP, highlights the nation's progressive approach towards creating a more inclusive and gender-equal research environment.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Create a set of indicators tailored to the national level for monitoring GE

Given the unique socio-cultural context of Romania, it is essential to have a set of indicators that reflect the specific challenges and opportunities related to gender equality in the country.

Establish a national mechanism or appoint contact points and external evaluators to the GEP activities

This will ensure a standardized approach to evaluating GEPs and provide research organizations with clear guidelines and benchmarks.

Allocate national resources for meetings with other national/international institutions to discuss issues and find solutions on the GEP implementation, monitoring, and evaluation

Collaborative discussions can lead to the sharing of promising practices and innovative solutions.

Allocate national resources to trainings for RPOs on the topic for the GEP implementation, monitoring, and evaluation

Continuous training ensures that research organizations are up to date with the latest methodologies and promising and/or best practices.

Create a national public database of GEP and/or good GE practices

A centralized database will serve as a valuable resource for research organizations, allowing them to learn from successful implementations and adapt promising and/or best practices to their context.

Conclusion

UEFISCDI's pioneering journey in the development and implementation of a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) stands as a testament to the institution's commitment to fostering a more inclusive and equitable research environment in Romania.

As the first Romanian public institution to embark on this transformative path, UEFISCDI has not only set a benchmark for others to follow but has also actively assisted other Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) in their endeavors to develop their own GEPs. Recognizing the importance of knowledge sharing and collaboration, UEFISCDI established the platform www.gep.uefiscdi.ro, which serves as a valuable resource hub, showcasing methodologies, results, and best practices. This initiative underscores the institution's vision of creating a ripple effect, where the principles of gender equality are not just confined to one organization but are embraced and integrated across the broader Romanian research landscape.

The institutional actions carried out within the CALIPER's lifecycle put forward valuable good practices that the UEFISCDI recognizes as key interventions with upscaling potential at national level.

3.2.8 Yasar University (YU)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

GEPs are not explicitly mandated for research organizations in Turkey by specific national laws or policies. However, it's essential to note that the *Article 10* of Turkish Constitution, includes a provision emphasizing the positive obligation of the state to implement gender equality. This constitutional commitment underscores the importance of gender equality and non-discrimination for all public and private sectors in Turkey.

Therefore, these constitutional provisions, as well as the commitments stemming from being a signatory of [CEDAW](#), serves as a foundation for promoting gender equality in all aspects of Turkish society, including research and academic institutions. It implies that all organizations should take measures to ensure gender equality without discriminating against any gender.

Also, since having Gender Equality Plan (GEP) is mandatory for public bodies, research organisations, or higher education institutions that participate in Horizon Europe Programme as of 2022, Turkish Council of Higher Education shared a recommendation paper suggesting that all the higher education institutions should start the adoption process of institutional GEPs.

The establishment of a quality policy and process by the Turkish Council of Higher Education (Yükseköğretim Kurulu - YÖK) indeed creates a favourable environment for the development, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) in Turkish universities and research institutions. But it should be noted that there is no established national or regional support on the GEPs design, implementation, monitoring and assessment; and neither an existing GEP audit system.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Quality policies often require institutions to collect and analyse data to ensure that they meet certain standards and objectives. In this context, data collection related to gender equality can be integrated into the quality assessment process. This allows for the regular collection of institutional data related to gender representation, pay equity, and other gender-related aspects, which can be used for GEP monitoring and evaluation.

The establishment of institutional quality departments and mechanisms can provide a structured framework for overseeing and promoting various aspects of institutional quality, including gender equality.

Hence the above, the following support mechanisms and practices could be developed at the national level:

Policy Guidance and Coordination
Establishing clear national guidelines and coordination mechanisms to ensure that GEPs align with broader gender equality policies and initiatives, making it mandatory for organizations to adhere to these plans.
Capacity Building
Providing training and resources for organizations to develop, implement, and monitor GEPs effectively, fostering a culture of gender sensitivity and competence.
Data Collection and Reporting
Encouraging standardized data collection on gender-related metrics, ensuring that organizations regularly report their progress on GEP objectives and providing tools and platforms for easy data

submission. Suggested indicators for the monitoring of Gender Equality in national context could be as follows:

- a. *Gender Representation:*
 - *Percentage of women in leadership roles (rectors, deans, department heads).*
 - *Gender distribution among staff or faculty members*
- b. *Recruitment and Promotion:*
 - *Gender distribution of recruitments*
 - *Gender distribution of appointments to leadership positions*
 - *Promotion rates by gender within academic and research staff*
- c. *Salary and Compensation:*
 - *Gender pay gap among research staff*
 - *Equal pay for equal work: Comparing the salaries of individuals in similar positions with similar qualifications.*
- d. *Research Funding and Grants:*
 - *Gender distribution of national research grant recipients.*
 - *Gender distribution of funding allocations for research projects.*
 - *Gender distribution of research staff awarded at the national level.*
- e. *Work-Life Balance and Support:*
 - *Monitoring practices and support mechanisms for work-life balance, such as flexible working hours*
 - *Institutional policies supporting maternal I& paternal rights*
- f. *Training and Development:*
 - *Trainings offered with the focus on gender equality & intersectionality*
 - *Opportunities for professional development and training, including mentorship and sponsorship programs*
- g. *Gender-Based Discrimination and Harassment:*
 - *Reported cases of gender-based discrimination and harassment.*
 - *Effectiveness of mechanisms in place to address such cases.*
- h. *Inclusion of gender-related topics in the curriculum*
 - *Courses offered in different levels related to gender issues and equality*
 - *Research projects and publications related to gender issues and equality*
- i. *Student Enrollment and Performance:*
 - *Gender distribution among students in various academic programs.*
 - *Gender differences in academic performance and graduation rates.*

These indicators may provide a holistic view of gender equality within research institutions and universities, covering aspects such as representation, work conditions, policies and practices. Regularly collecting and analysing data based on these indicators can help track progress and identify areas that may require attention and improvement in promoting gender equality.

Peer Reviews and Benchmarking

Promoting peer review mechanisms among R&I organizations to share best practices, learning from each other's experiences, and benchmarking progress against peers and international standards.

Diversity and Inclusion Initiatives

Encouraging R&I organizations to implement strategies that go beyond gender binary norms, aiming for inclusivity that considers all forms of diversity, including LGBTQ+ individuals and intersectionality.

Financial Incentives

Offering financial incentives or grants to organizations that successfully implement and demonstrate tangible progress in their GEPs, motivating participation and compliance.

Independent Audits and Evaluation

Conducting independent evaluations of GEPs to ensure transparency and credibility, fostering trust in the monitoring process and facilitating corrective actions as needed.

Stakeholder Engagement

Facilitating the involvement of all relevant stakeholders, including researchers, employees, and the broader community, to ensure that GEPs are comprehensive and address the full spectrum of gender equality issues.

Awareness Campaigns

Launching national awareness campaigns to promote the importance of GEPs and gender equality in research and innovation, creating a supportive environment for change.

Conclusion

Projects conducted within the scope of the European Union's framework programs, including FP7, Horizon 2020, and more recently, Horizon Europe, have undeniably played an important role in advancing the development and implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) within Research and Innovation (R&I) institutions in Turkey. The collaboration with the CALIPER project has proven instrumental for Yaşar University in the formulation and successful implementation of its first GEP.

While in Turkey GEPs are not explicitly mandated by specific national laws or policies, the Turkish Constitution's Article 10 underscores the government's commitment to gender equality, creating a foundational framework for promoting these plans across all sectors, both public and private.

Furthermore, the requirement for public bodies, research organizations, and higher education institutions participating in the Horizon Europe Programme to adopt institutional GEPs highlights a growing awareness of the importance of gender equality in research and academia.

The absence of national or regional support mechanisms for GEP design, implementation, monitoring, and evaluation calls for establishing a supportive framework with clear national guidelines, capacity-building programs, standardized data collection, peer reviews, financial incentives, and independent audits.

Additionally, introducing a national audit system for implemented GEPs would contribute to transparent monitoring and evaluation, further promoting trust and accountability in the gender equality process.

To strengthen gender equality initiatives at the national level, it is recommended that various support mechanisms and practices be developed, such as capacity building trainings, standardized data collection and

reporting, peer reviews, diversity and inclusion initiatives, financial incentives, independent audits, stakeholder engagement, and awareness campaigns. These measures would collectively contribute to the advancement of gender equality in Turkish research and innovation, fostering a more inclusive and equitable environment for all stakeholders involved.

3.2.9 Salento University (UNILE)

National context on evaluation procedures of inclusive GEP

Since 2021, GEPs, have become mandatory under European law, in order to access ERC funding. The national rectors's conference (CRUI), a governance body overseeing the Italian universities, has published guidelines for the set-up of gender budgets and GEPS². As a matter of fact, UNILE CALIPER partners contributed to the panel that was assigned with the preparation of the guidelines, representing the University of Salento. In this guidelines document key performance indicators about the monitoring and evaluation of GEPs as also suggested. In this context, the Ministry collects gender budgets and GEPS in a repository.

There is not any national/regional system that audits the implemented GEPs. It would be obviously beneficial to check the soundness and completeness of GEPs and their actual implementation: there are guidelines and the universities upload gender budgets and GEPS in a national repository.

Recommendations on monitoring and evaluating inclusive GEPs at the national level

Allocate human and financial resources with special focus on monitoring of GEPs' implementation

It would be crucial for the Universities to have access to national funding, so that they can hire, and train dedicated staff to monitor GEPS and assist in the implementation. A national audit and incentives to virtuous RPOs implementing GEPs and good practices is also fundamental.

Conclusion

Within the CALIPER project UNILE has enhanced its Gender Equality Strategy. Examples of the introduced improvements revolve around the enrolment and retention of women in science, the implementation of work-life balance policies, and removing obstacles to women's career progression. Following the project's plan, UNILE carried out a structured monitoring and evaluation process, which, in conjunction with the national regulatory context, made prominent that a rigorous GEP monitoring and evaluation can be sustained by allocating specific human and financial resources in universities. In this respect, having dedicated funding/budget in national level plays an important role in order for universities to afford staff assigned with keeping track of GEP actions and coordinating their implementation. In addition to affording dedicated staff within universities for the task of monitoring and evaluating GEP actions, a national auditing system/framework is also a fundamental step forward.

² [Vade mecum for the development of the Gender Equality Plan in Italian Universities](#)

4. Conclusion and comments

This deliverable is the third set of policy briefings developed under the support of the CALIPER project. This final version contains concrete information based on the CALIPER experience from the evaluation phase and discusses on the evidence and results of the first iteration phase as well as the refinement process and the results of the whole monitoring and evaluation phase of GEPs in the project's RPOs and RFOs.

Several concepts and suggestions have been put forward by the GEP implementing RPOs and RFOs of the project drawing from their unique experiences. Overall, the project partners have put emphasis on the existence of a standardised procedure for GEPs' monitoring and evaluation under the coordination and supervision of a dedicated governmental mechanism. Many of their recommendations revolve around the establishment of committees and/or bodies under the jurisdiction of government that are assigned with the overall monitoring and coordination of GEPs' implementation in research organisations. In this respect, the standardisation of GEPs' design and tracking based on guidelines and indicators concretely provided by such bodies has also been a shared point, while the creation of a central platform/database as a reference point of instructions and best practises for GEP implementing organisations has been a re-occurring concept.

